

Data download from the ERGA Pilot repository

Downloading data from the ERGA repository is very simple. Data can be retrieved using provided urls if the data has been made public or shared with you by the owner. If this is not the case or you wish to download multiple datasets programmatically using the command line you need an account first. If you do not have an account yet, you can request one to José Fernández (jose.m.fernandez@bsc.es). Once you have an account you can login using this website: <https://ergapilot.bsc.es>

Nextcloud contents can be accessed and managed through WebDAV, and WebDAV is a superset of common HTTP commands. You can use `curl` for simple downloads:

```
curl -u ${username}:${password/app_password} -O
https://ergapilot.bsc.es/remote.php/webdav/ERGAPilot/species/Alburnus_alburnus/fAlbAlb1/fAlbAlb1_pb_stats.yaml
```

! Important note: it is advisable to create an app password, so your main credentials are unlinked from the ones used for a specific purpose, like command line downloading. This is required if you set up 2-factor authentication in your account.

Downloading data programmatically

For recursive downloads you can use [nextcloudcmd](#), which is available in Ubuntu through package [nextcloud-desktop-cmd](#). Note that recursive download example is assuming the destination `/localdir` must be an existing but empty directory. This is important in the case of `nextcloudcmd`, in order to assure a server to local synchronization:

```
nextcloudcmd -u ${username} -p ${password/app_password} --non-interactive /localdir
https://ergapilot.bsc.es/remote.php/webdav/ERGAPilot/species/${species}
```

Alternatively, you can use any WebDAV client supporting recursive download capabilities, or temporarily mount the directory with `davfs2` in read only mode, and issue your favorite command line recursive copy command. Note: `cadaver` WebDAV client does not seem to fully support recursive download through `mget`.

Data upload to the ERGA Pilot repository

Sharing your data with the rest of the ERGA community is also very simple. If you do not have an account yet, first request an account to José Fernández (jose.m.fernandez@bsc.es).

Once you have an account you can login using this website:

<https://ergapilot.bsc.es>

Note that the GUI limits the size of files that can be uploaded. Upload using the command line should be preferred for large files.

A straightforward way to upload a file is the following:

```
curl -u ${Username}:${password} -T "https://ergapilot.bsc.es/remote.php/webdav/${path_to_file}"
```

Example:

```
curl -u sagane.dind:abcd -T test.fastq.gz "https://ergapilot.bsc.es/remote.php/webdav/ERGAPilot/species/Epeorus_asimilis/fEpeAss1/genomic_data/pacbio/test.fastq.gz"
```

For alternative methods and more information check the manual:

https://docs.nextcloud.com/server/22/user_manual/en/files/access_webdav.html

Please upload your files using the following data structure:

ergapilot.bsc.es

Raw genomic data

```
ERGAPilot/species/  
└─ Alburnus_alburnus/  
  └─ fAlbAlb1/  
    └─ genomic_data/  
      └─ pacbio  
      └─ arima/  
      └─ dovetail/  
      └─ phase/
```

Assembly fasta files and intermediates

```
ERGAPilot/species/  
└─ Alburnus_alburnus/  
  └─ fAlbAlb1/  
    └─ genomic_data/  
      └─ assembly_vgp_standard_2.0/  
        └─ fAlbAlb1.pri.asm.20211120.fasta.gz  
        └─ fAlbAlb1.alt.asm.20211120.fasta.gz  
        └─ evaluation/  
          └─ c/  
            └─ Merqury/  
            └─ BUSCO/  
          └─ p/  
            └─ ...  
      └─ intermediates/  
        └─ fAlbAlb1_c1.fasta.gz  
        └─ fAlbAlb1_c2.fasta.gz  
        └─ fAlbAlb1_...fasta.gz  
        └─ hifiasm/  
        └─ purge_dups/  
        └─ salsa/
```